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Evaluation of antimicrobial and biocompatible properties of nanocomposites

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Abstract. Nanocomposite materials developed for medical and industrial applications should meet specific requirements for antimicrobial properties and biocompatibility. The objective was to evaluate antimicrobial and cytotoxic effects of various types of newly engineered nanomaterials (nanofillers, polymer composite films). Antimicrobial analyses were performed using the broth microdilution method, disk and well diffusion tests and plate count method on potentially pathogenic bacterial gram-positive (G+) strains (methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus salivarius*, *Staphylococcus aureus*), gram-negative (G-) strains (*Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus mirabilis*) and yeast strains (*Candida albicans*, *Candida parapsilosis*). The inhibitory effect of the composites on biofilm formation was determined by the Crystal violet biofilm assay. The biocompatibility of the composites was determined by *in vitro* MTT cell viability assay, Lactate dehydrogenase test and Neutral red uptake assay with cell line A549. Antimicrobial and biocompatibility assessment, using a complex of detection assays, provided important information regarding the potential use of these nanomaterials for medicine or industrial purposes.

1. Introduction

Composite materials containing nanoparticles (NPs) have a wide range of applications in various fields, including medicine, food industry, wastewater treatment, cosmetics, or electronics. A significant characteristic of NPs may be their antimicrobial activity against multidrug resistant microorganisms. However, the increasing use of nanomaterials also raises concerns about their potential toxicity and long-term safety [1].

In this study, the antimicrobial and cytotoxic effects of composites containing fillers based on graphene oxide (GO), vermiculite (VMT) or kaolinite (K), which were modified with silver (Ag NPs), zinc oxide (ZnO NPs), zinc sulfide (ZnS NPs), and hexadecylpyridinium (HDP) or hexadecyltrimethylammonium (HDTMA) cations were evaluated. The antimicrobial efficacy of the newly prepared composites was determined using antimicrobial methods on potentially pathogenic bacteria and yeast. The composites were also studied in terms of their ability to inhibit the formation of bacterial biofilms. The detection of the cytotoxic potential of the composites and their degradation leachates was performed using *in vitro* cytotoxicity tests.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Nanomaterials

Nanoparticles (Ag NPs, ZnO NPs, ZnS NPs), composite fillers (VMT+Ag, VMT+ZnO, VMT+HDTMA, VMT+HDP, K+ZnS, GO+Ag), polymer composite films based on polylactide (PLA+VMT+Ag, PLA+VMT+HDP, PLA+VMT+HDTMA, PLA+GO+Ag), and also the leachates of the polymer composites after one to six months of degradation were tested [2,3].

2.2 Microbial strains and cell culture

Bacterial gram-negative strains *Acinetobacter baumannii* (CCM 7117), *Escherichia coli* (CCM 3988), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (CCM 1960), *Proteus mirabilis* (CCM 7188), gram-positive strains methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA, CCM 7111), *Staphylococcus aureus* (CCM 4223), *Streptococcus salivarius* (CCM 4046) and yeast strains *Candida albicans* (CCM 8186), *Candida parapsilosis* (CCM 8260) were obtained from the Czech Collection of Microorganisms (Brno, Czech Republic). Cell line A549 was obtained from the European Collection of Cell Cultures (ECACC, Sigma-Aldrich, USA).

2.3 Methods to evaluate the antimicrobial activity and biocompatibility of composites

Detection of antimicrobial effects of the nanomaterials was performed using microbial tests on potentially pathogenic gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, as well as yeast strains (Figure 1). Antibacterial and antifungal effects were detected using disk and well diffusion methods, the microdilution method, and the plate count method with colony forming units determination [4,5,6]. Antibiofilm effect was determined as an inhibitory effect on the formation of bacterial biofilms using the Christensen method and also the autoaggregation and motility tests [7,8].

Another large group of tests included cytotoxicity tests with cell lines. The cytotoxic effect was examined by the MTT assay, Neutral red uptake (NRU) assay and Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) test. The tests were performed in both contact and extraction variants [9].

Figure 1. Methods using for the assessment of the antimicrobial properties and biocompatibility of composites.

3. Results

3.1 Qualitative screening of antimicrobial effect of composites

The antimicrobial activity of the samples was performed using the disk (or well) diffusion method. Figure 2 shows the results of the inhibitory effect of the VMT+Ag nanofiller on the growth of bacterial strains *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, and *S. salivarius*. The susceptibility of bacteria to this nanofiller was evaluated by measuring the size of the inhibition zones. The nanofiller exhibited a significant antibacterial effect (zone size > 8 mm) for all bacterial strains, with a slight concentration dependence. Detection of the antimicrobial effect by the agar diffusion assay is orientation and screening method, and therefore it was necessary to use a more sensitive broth microdilution method to determine the minimal inhibition concentration (MIC) of antimicrobial fillers [2].

Figure 2. Detection of antibacterial effect of VMT+Ag nanofiller against strains *E. coli* (A), *P. aeruginosa* (B), *S. aureus* (C), *S. salivarius* (D). Numbers 1-4 indicate the concentration of the sample (1: 37 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disk}$, 2: 74 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disk}$, 3: 111 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disk}$, 4: 148 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disk}$).

3.2 Quantitative determination of antimicrobial activity of composites

A more precise test for the assessment of antimicrobial effect was the plate count method, which was used to detect the number of viable cells in a sample. After incubation of the sample with microbial strain, the sample was diluted in a series of dilutions and then aliquots of the dilutions were spread on agar growth medium. The numbers of colonies obtained on the agar plates were expressed as colony forming units per ml (cfu/ml). The inhibitory effect of growth was evaluated as a reduction in the number of colonies compared to the control, i.e. the strain without the sample. Figure 3 shows the results of the effect of the VMT+ZnO nanocomposite on the growth of yeast. In the case of a concentration of 30 mg/ml, the inhibitory efficiency exceeded 99.6 %.

Figure 3. Antifungal effect of VMT+ZnO nanocomposite using the plate count method.

3.3 Inhibitory effect of polylactide composites on biofilm formation

The greatest contribution to the antimicrobial evaluation was the detection of the inhibitory effect of PLA composites after all degradation times on the formation of bacterial biofilms. The specific structure of biofilms results in increased resistance of bacteria to antibacterial agents, so there is currently a need to look for new materials with biofilm-inhibiting properties [10]. Biofilm formation was quantified by the Crystal violet microtiter plate assay. The PLA and PLA+GO, PLA+VMT composites showed no inhibitory effect on biofilm formation [3].

An interesting finding was the difference between silver-containing composites (Figure 4). In the case of the composite PLA+VMT+Ag, strong inhibition of biofilm formation was observed in all bacterial strains. On the PLA+GO+Ag composite, weaker biofilm inhibition was observed in *E. coli* and especially *P. aeruginosa*. The most sensitive strain was *Staphylococcus aureus*. Inhibition of biofilm formation was also found on the PLA composites containing VMT+HDP or VMT+HDTMA. In the case of the PLA+VMT+HDTMA composite, no inhibitory effect was detected against *P. aeruginosa* strain [3].

Figure 4. Inhibitory effect of polylactide-based composites on the formation of bacterial biofilms. PC - positive control, bacterial biofilm in nutrient medium without sample; NC - negative control, composite sample in nutrient medium without microbial strain; M - month (time of degradation). *Indicates a significant statistical difference ($p < 0.05$) between the microbial strain affected by the sample and the positive control.

3.4 Assessment of the biocompatible properties of polylactide composites

The biocompatibility of PLA composites and their degradation leachates (1, 3, 6 months) was evaluated using the *in vitro* MTT assay [11,12]. The sample is considered cytotoxic if cell viability falls below 70 % of control viability (untreated cells) [13]. The cytotoxic effect of the composites themselves was not demonstrated in either the contact or extraction test [3]. Figure 5 shows the results of the testing of the leachates from PLA composites. Only PLA+VMT+HDP leachate obtained after 6 months of degradation significantly reduced cell viability to 7.6 %. These results show that during the 6-month degradation of the composite, a toxic HDP concentration was released into the leachate.

Figure 5. Inhibitory effect of leachates of PLA composites on A549 cell viability using MTT assay. M - month (time of degradation).

4. Conclusions

All six studied nanofillers showed an inhibitory effect on the growth of bacterial and yeast strains. The highest inhibitory activity on the formation of bacterial biofilms was detected in the polylactide composite containing nanofiller VMT+Ag.

In both contact and extraction tests, no cytotoxic effect was demonstrated for any of the polylactide composites.

In degradation leachates from PLA composites, a significant decrease in cell viability was found only in PLA+VMT+HDP after 6 months of degradation.

Antimicrobial and biocompatibility assessment, using a complex of detection assays, provided important information on the potential use of these composites for medicine or industrial purposes.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in repository ZENODO at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15690596>.

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